

Deliverable n.	1.1
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3.1 LinkedIn	Errore. Il segnalibro non è definito.
3.2 X / Twitter	Errore. Il segnalibro non è definito.
3.3 Bluesky	Errore. Il segnalibro non è definito.

1. Deliverable abstract

This deliverable aims to present the tools developed for JUMP INTO SPACE to ensure a high-quality communication and dissemination during its execution. This includes a logo, a website, social media accounts as well as templates for the powerpoint presentations. Its use by all the partners will greatly increase the project's visibility and help the project's "identity" to be known and recognizable by all the stakeholders.

These tools aim to provide support to all partners to ensure the dissemination and communication of the project's results into European and global audience, both in the field (solar cells and/or space research entities, e.g. universities and research centers; PV and space market and industry) and non-specialised (general public). This task runs during the whole project duration from the very beginning, to achieve as early as possible grounding toward successful communication, dissemination and exploitation of the project's results within and outside the consortium.

2. Logo and website

2.1 Logo

A logo was designed to visually summarize the project's main objectives, opting for an artistic rather than didactic approach.

Figure 1. JUMP INTO SPACE logo.

2.2 Website

A website has been created to present JUMP INTO SPACE objectives and activities: <https://www.jumpintospace.eu/>.

It is going to be the project's main digital communication channel and will be updated on a regular basis. It aims to present the project in a visual and attractive way but with scientific rigor.

The main page features the project title, a table of contents showing the targeted main topics and a short summary of the project, including the objectives. Visitors can then navigate to the Project page, with a more detailed explanation of the project; to the Partners page, where each partner has a section with logo, website and short description; to the News page, which contain the news list, each one with a link to read further. The news section will be updated regularly with relevant news related to the project, such as meetings, publication of papers, participation to conferences, etc. Results that can be disseminated will also be published to inform the stakeholders and the general public. Finally, there is a page with contact details in the form of an info email account, while the links to social media accounts are at the bottom of each page.

Figure 2. JUMP INTO SPACE website: (from left to right) main page, Partners page, detail of a Partner information box.

3. Social media accounts

The social media accounts were created to communicate smaller pieces of news and to amplify the ones published on the website, to interact with stakeholders, especially academic and industrial in the field of perovskite solar cells and space, to connect to EIC/EISMEA and other Portfolio members, and to raise awareness around JUMP INTO SPACE even in the non-specialized audience and general public.

All members of the consortium are encouraged to actively provide content, re-launch posts published by JUMP INTO SPACE accounts, and also post about their activities within the project, tagging JUMP INTO SPACE accounts, to position JUMP INTO SPACE as a reference in the field.

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/jump-into-space/>

Figure 3. LinkedIn page.

X/Twitter: <https://x.com/JumpIntoSpaceEU>

Figure 4. X/Twitter account.

Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/jumpintospaceeueic.bsky.social>

Figure 5. Bluesky account.

4. Templates

A template for power point presentation has been prepared for the Space Portfolio kick off meeting and then provided to partners ahead of the project kick off meeting. It has been adopted for all types of communication and dissemination activities for the entire duration of the project (e.g. project meetings, conferences, seminars, workshops, etc.).

JUMP INTO SPACE Kick-off meeting

WPx : Title
Rome, 14th November 2024

Logos: European Innovation Council, SAULE TECHNOLOGIES, HZB Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin, ONERA, UNINOVA

WPx – Actions from (previous) meeting

WHO	WHAT	WHEN	STATUS
Action 1		Mxx	DONE/ IN PROGRESS
Action 2			
Action 3			
Action 4			

WPx – Next Steps

WHO	WHAT	WHEN
Action 1		Mxx - Myy
Action 2		
Action 3		

Thank you for your attention

Name
Email

Website: <https://www.jumpintospace.eu/>
 LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/jump-into-space/>
 X/Twitter: @JumpIntoSpaceEU
 Bluesky: @jumpintospaceeueic.bsky.social

Figure 6. Template for powerpoint presentation: examples.